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Do ESG Factors Influence Risk-Adjusted Return on Equity? Evidence from the Nigeria Banking Sector

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Abstract: *This study investigated the impact of Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) factors on the performance of Nigerian deposit money banks, using risk-adjusted return on equity (RAROE) as the primary measure. While previous research has focused on developed economies using traditional profitability metrics like return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE), the incorporate risk-adjusted measures to account for financial volatility using Nigerian deposit money banks data from 2012 to 2022. The study employed panel data regression models with E-views 12 and Python library to analyse the data. The findings reveal that environmental resource efficiency positively impacts bank performance, while emissions and waste reduction have a negative effect, indicating a trade-off between sustainability efforts and financial returns. Environmental innovation has an insignificant relationship, suggesting the need for cautious adoption of green initiatives. Workforce development and community engagement enhance performance, while human rights policies show no significant impact. In governance, stakeholder rights and management oversight influence profitability, but bank size negatively affects performance, challenging the economies of scale assumption in Nigeria's banking sector. The recommend that Nigerian banks integrate ESG principles strategically, optimize environmental sustainability efforts and strengthen governance structures to align with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) while improving financial stability.*

Keywords: *ESG; Risk-Adjusted Return on Equity (RAROE); Bank Performance; Nigeria, Sustainable Banking.*

1. Introduction

Nigeria, Africa's largest economy with a GDP of USD 477.38 billion in 2022 (World Bank, 2023; NBS, 2023), boasts a diverse financial sector (International Monetary Fund, 2023) and shares many of the economic characteristics typical of emerging markets. These features continue to attract international investors, making Nigeria a key destination for foreign investment (Michael, 2023; Mogaji, 2023). Its financial market mirrors those of other emerging economies such as Brazil (\$1.44 trillion), Indonesia (\$1.06 trillion), Thailand (\$460 billion), and South Africa (\$420 billion) in terms of market development and regulatory strides. Notably, the Nigerian banking sector has demonstrated commitment to global

sustainable development goals through the Central Bank of Nigeria's 2012 Sustainable Banking Principles (SBPs). However, it remains burdened by a maladapted regulatory environment, corporate governance challenges, and systemic risk exposure. Despite these issues, the sector continues to play a vital role in financial intermediation, inclusion, advisory services, and economic development—key channels through which ESG impacts are realized.

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) has emerged as a significant global concept, driven by the need for more balanced institutional and business operations. This growing focus has led to a wave of transformation, compelling organizations to integrate ESG considerations into their strategies as a framework for fostering sustainability and ethical practices (Buallay, 2019; Buallay et al., 2020; Amel-Zadeh and Serafeim, 2018). The environmental component centers on how companies manage their ecological footprint, promoting climate change mitigation, carbon emission reduction, and environmentally responsible practices (Clark et al., 2015). As noted by Ben Abdallah and Bahloul (2025), this component has gained increasing relevance over the past decade, with ecological issues taking center stage in global discourse. Notably, financial institutions, especially banks, play a critical role in financing projects that influence environmental transformation. With investors becoming more climate-conscious, banks with strong environmental commitments tend to earn greater investor trust. This is particularly relevant in developing economies, where pollution and air quality are pressing concerns. As such, banks that implement environmental sustainability initiatives are increasingly viewed as contributors to community welfare (Maama, 2021).

The social dimension of ESG highlights corporate responsibility in areas such as labor practices, human rights, diversity, and community engagement. Leading organizations recognize the direct link between social responsibility and long-term sustainability, acknowledging that employee well-being and strong community ties are vital to business success. Emphasizing social impact involves initiatives that improve workplace conditions, promote diversity and inclusion, and engage local communities to meet their needs. In today's business landscape, diversity and inclusion are key drivers of innovation and performance (Clyde & Co., 2022). As Chang et al. (2021) noted, a diverse workforce fosters inclusivity, creativity, and better problem-solving. Organizations that prioritize diversity align with ethical standards and societal expectations, thereby strengthening reputation and stakeholder trust.

The governance aspect of ESG focuses on corporate structures and practices that promote accountability, ethical decision-making, and the integration of sustainability. It assesses how effectively a company's governance framework enables it to address environmental and social issues while ensuring long-term financial stability. Strong governance supports transparency, mitigates risks, and upholds ethical standards (Cornett et al., 2016). As Dikau and Volz (2021) observed, awareness of sustainability issues among businesses and financial institutions is growing, leading organizations to adopt strategies such as staff training on climate change, waste management, and pollution control. Companies are also aligning strategic plans with broader environmental and social goals. To institutionalize sustainability, firms must embed all three ESG pillars into their operations, policies, and strategic frameworks (COSO, 2018).

Risk-adjusted return on equity (RAROE) is a crucial metric for evaluating bank performance, as it accounts for both profitability and risk exposure. However, given the multifaceted nature of banking sector performance, various scholars have employed different indicators to assess bank performance. For instance, Return on Assets (ROA) has been utilized by Ozili and Uadiale (2017), Demaki (2018) and Abdulazeez et al. (2016), while Return on Equity (ROE) has been explored by Onakoya, Fasanya and Ofoegbu (2014) as well as Ozili and Uadiale (2017). Additionally, Net Interest Margin (NIM) has been examined by Adekunle and Aghedo (2014) and Ozili and Uadiale (2017). Tobin's Q, another performance metric, has been analyzed by Gugong, Arugu and Dandago (2014), Adenikinju (2012) and Ujunwa (2012). Meanwhile, recurring earnings power (REP) was adopted in the study by Ozili and Uadiale (2017), whereas earnings per share (EPS) was investigated by Adefemi et al. (2018) as well as Shittu, Ahmad and Ishak (2018).

Nevertheless, most existing measures often fail to adequately account for the risks and volatility associated with returns. As a major contribution, this study adopts Risk-Adjusted Return on Equity (RAROE) over traditional ROE, as it captures inherent uncertainties and directly links a bank's net

income to its equity while adjusting for risk exposure and volatility. RAROE is calculated by dividing ROE by its standard deviation, thus offering a refined perspective on financial performance. Prior studies (Baek et al., 2015; Baek et al., 2018) have used risk-adjusted returns to enhance financial evaluation. The evolution of such frameworks marks a significant advancement in assessing bank performance by integrating risk management. This study sets itself apart from prior research in developed countries (Buallay, 2019; Maama, 2021; Giannopoulos et al., 2022) by incorporating RAROE to provide a more comprehensive framework for understanding how ESG influences Risk-Adjusted Return on Equity, thereby contributing to empirical studies on ESG and bank performance in an emerging economy like Nigeria. The remainder of this paper follows a structured format: Section two encompasses the literature review, while Section three outlines the methodology employed. Section four presents and discusses the results and the final section provides the conclusion.

2. Empirical Review

This study hinged on stakeholder theory. Stakeholders' theory was pronounced by Freeman's in 1984 in his landmark book "Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach", while various authors like (Donaldson and Preston, 1995; Mitchell et al., 1997) have contributed to the theory and therefore making notion of stakeholders embedded in management scholarship and in managers' thinking. Freeman (1984) submitted that the firm exists for the purpose of serving stakeholders' interests and therefore organization should emphasis on the development and maintenance of all stakeholder relationships, not just the shareholders has required by law but also have duties to key stakeholder groups such as customers, employees, communities, suppliers, etc. The study of (Edmans,2020; Freeman, Harrison and Zylidopoulos, (2018) submitted that stakeholder theory believed in an holistic approach to business aligning with the objectives environmental, social and governance (ESG) that emphasized on the consideration of different stakeholders interests especially those that are align with environmental sustainability, social equity and governance to achieve inclusiveness.

Simsek and Cankaya (2021) analysed the link between ESG scores and bank performance in G8 nations. Using ROA and ROE as financial metrics, they found that environmental and governance scores had a negative impact, while the social score showed a positive effect. However, their overall model lacked statistical significance. A key limitation was the inability to assess country-specific variations. Azmi et al. (2021) examined the ESG–performance relationship in emerging economies using a two-step GMM approach. Their findings revealed a nonlinear, inverted U-shaped relationship, indicating that ESG activities initially boost net interest margin but may yield diminishing returns beyond a certain point. The study called for further research to determine the exact threshold where ESG benefits start to decline. Buallay (2019) explored the impact of ESG practices on bank operations and found an overall positive relationship. While environmental disclosure improved ROA and Tobin's Q, CSR disclosure had a negative effect across models. A key research gap was the omission of other factors that may influence sustainable reporting practices.

Shakil et al. (2019) analysed ESG and bank performance in emerging markets between 2015 and 2018 using GMM. They found that environmental and social factors positively influenced financial performance, while governance had no significant effect. The study suggested that banks should invest in ESG activities but did not address the link between ESG and financial risk. However, Miralles-Quirós et al. (2019) examined how ESG performance impacts stock prices in the banking sector from 2002 to 2015. Their findings indicated a positive link between environmental and governance performance and share prices, while social performance had a negative effect. The study suggested that ESG became more valuable to financial stakeholders after the global financial crisis but was limited by its focus on commercial banks in developed markets. Furthermore, Gangi et al. (2018) investigated the relationship between sustainable development, corporate governance and risk in 142 banks across 35 countries (2011–2015). They found that strong corporate governance enhances environmental engagement, which in turn reduces operational risk. Jo et al. (2015) studied corporate environmental responsibility in 29 countries and found that reducing environmental costs leads to improved financial performance, but this effect takes 1–2 years. The study noted that developed markets experience faster financial benefits than developing ones.

Additionally, Amel-Zadeh and Serafeim (2018) surveyed investors on how they use ESG information. Most institutional investors prioritized financial gains over ethical concerns. The study emphasized the material relevance of ESG data in investment decisions but acknowledged the potential bias in survey responses. Ferrero-Ferrero et al. (2016) analysed ESG consistency in EU-15 firms (2002–2011) using GMM. They found that firms with consistent ESG performance achieved better economic outcomes, especially at higher ESG levels. The study also noted that firms focusing on specific ESG categories were not penalized by the market. Laguir et al. (2018) examined the relationship between financial and environmental performance in French banks (2008–2011). Their findings suggested a bidirectional link, where strong financial performance supported environmental commitment and vice versa. However, the study lacked multiple ESG rating systems for broader validation.

3. Methodology

The study utilized both descriptive and inferential statistics to assess the relationship between environmental, social and governance (ESG) factors and bank performance in Nigeria with the aid of panel data regression analysis. Secondary data were obtained from the annual reports of twelve (12) Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) publicly traded on the Nigerian Exchange as of December 31, 2022. Interestingly, this period encompasses significant regulatory changes, including the 2014 CBN Code, economic fluctuations. Furthermore, it marks a phase of governance stability, recovery from the 2008 financial crisis and the initiation of the Sustainable Banking Principles by the Central Bank of Nigeria in 2012.

3.1. Estimation Technique, Model and Variables Specification

Panel data modelling techniques are commonly used in studies on corporate performance in the banking sector (Maqbool and Zameer, 2018; Buallay, 2019; Buallay et al., 2020; Weber, 2011). Weber (2011) suggested that utilizing panel regressions offers a distinct advantage in managing unobserved heterogeneity, whether in fixed or random models. Additionally, panel data provides a significant volume of data points, thereby reducing col-linearity issues among independent variables and increasing the degrees of freedom.

The study conducted a Chow test to evaluate the suitability of either the fixed or random effects model. Fixed effects models are specifically designed to examine variability within individual units. In the context of panel regression with fixed effects, the assumption is made that the intercept is not stochastic due to notable disparities across firms regarding their underlying levels of the dependent variable. On the other hand, random effects models allow for exploration of variations both among companies within the same year and within each company over time. If the null hypothesis is rejected, the random effects model is considered unsuitable, thus favouring the use of fixed effects.

3.2. Model Specification

The model specification for this study is adopted from the work of Menicucci and Paolucci (2023), whose framework provides a structured approach to analysing influence of environmental social and governance variables and bank performance measured by risk adjusted return on average equity (RAROE). This study estimates three linear panel-data regressions to isolate the influence of environmental and social corporate responsibility, governance on bank profitability measured by risk adjusted return on average equity (RAROE) to capture volatility in bank return (Baek et al., 2018) that was not measured in the previous study of Menicucci and Paolucci (2023). Therefore, these studies aligned with the existing literature and enhances the validity of its empirical analysis.

$$M1: RAROE_{i,t} = (\alpha_0 + \beta_1 Env_ru_{i,t} + \beta_2 Env_Em_{i,t} + \beta_3 Env_In_{i,t} + \beta_4 LD_{i,t} + \beta_5 BS_{i,t} + \mu_t) \quad (1)$$

$$M2: RAROE_{i,t} = (\alpha_0 + \beta_1 Soc_wf_{i,t} + \beta_2 Soc_Hr_{i,t} + \beta_3 Soc_com_{i,t} + \beta_4 LD_{i,t} + \beta_5 BS_{i,t} + \mu_t) \quad (2)$$

$$M3: RAROE_{i,t} = (\alpha_0 + \beta_1 Gov_mo_{i,t} + \beta_2 Gov_shr_{i,t} + \beta_3 Gov_csr_{i,t} + \beta_4 LD_{i,t} + \beta_5 BS_{i,t} + \mu_t) \quad (3)$$

3.3. Variables Specification

This study examines the relationship between ESG practices and the financial performance of Nigerian deposit money banks, using Risk-Adjusted Return on Equity (RAROE) as the key performance metric. The selection of variables is grounded in stakeholder theory and the legitimacy theory, which posits that firms engaging in responsible practices gain legitimacy, investor trust, and long-term value. The variables are categorized as dependent, independent (grouped into environmental, social, and governance dimensions), and control variables. Each was selected based on theoretical grounding and previous empirical studies. Table 1 summarizes the description and measurement of each variable, with reference to previous empirical studies to justify their inclusion.

Table 1. Variables Description and Measurement

Variables	Description	Acronyms	Measurement/Justification and Theoretical Relevance	Expected Effect on RAROE
Dependent Variables	Risk-Adjusted Return on Equity	RAROE	Risk-Adjusted Return on Equity is calculated by dividing the return on equity by the standard deviation of equity returns, as detailed in Baek et al. 2018).	Positive
ESG Rating	Based on the weighted average of each of the components of the ESG pillar. The weight of each component is divided by the items found in the annual reports (balance sheet)			
Independent Variables	Environmental	ENV	<p><i>The relative sum of category weights for the environmental categories. It is based on three dimensions: ENV_Ru (resource use efficiency), ENV_Em (emission and waste reduction) and ENV_In (environmental innovation) aligning with the (Resource-Based Theory)</i></p> <p>ENV_Ru = bank's efficiency in reducing the use of materials, energy, or water and capacity to find more eco-efficient solutions for the business processes.</p> <p>ENV_Em = bank's commitment and effectiveness in reducing environmental emissions and waste in operational activities</p> <p>ENV_In = bank's capacity to reduce the environmental burdens and costs for its clients and to create new opportunities for eco-designed products and services</p>	<p>Positive</p> <p>Negative or Mixed</p> <p>Delayed or Negative</p>
	Social	SOC	<p><i>The relative sum of category weights for the social responsibility categories. It is based on four dimensions: SOC_Wf (workforce), SOC_Hr (human rights) and SOC_Com (community) supported by legitimacy theory.</i></p> <p>SOC_Wf = bank's effectiveness toward job satisfaction, a safe and</p>	

			<p>healthy workplace, while developing both equal and diverse opportunity</p> <p>SOC_Hr = bank's effectiveness in respecting fundamental human rights conventions.</p> <p>SOC_Com = bank's commitment to being a good citizen, respecting business ethics and protecting public health.</p>	<p>Negative</p> <p>Positive</p> <p>Positive</p>
	Governance	GOV	<p><i>The relative sum of category weights for the governance categories. It combines three dimensions: GOV_Mo (management and oversight), GOV_Shr (shareholders rights) and GOV_Csr (CSR strategy) aligns with agency theory</i></p> <p>GOV_Mo = bank's commitment and effectiveness in following governance principles.</p> <p>GOV_Shr = bank's effectiveness in treating its shareholders in an equal manner.</p> <p>GOV_Csr = bank's way of incorporating social and environmental dimensions in its decision-making processes</p>	<p>Positive</p> <p>Positive</p> <p>Negative</p>
Control Variables	Loans to total deposits	LOANDEP	<p>Loan-to-deposit is measured using a customer loan divided by a customer's deposit (Hapsari, 2018; Rengasamy, 2014).</p>	
	Bank Size	BankSize	<p>Bank size is measured using the natural logarithm of bank assets as used by past researchers (Abbas et al., 2019)</p>	

Author's Compilation (2024)

4. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

4.1. Descriptive Analysis

This section presents the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study. It provided a summary of the key characteristics of the dataset such as the mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values.

From Table 2, the descriptive analysis would be interpreted in three different strata which are the measure of central tendency, the measure of dispersion and the measure of normality. The mean, median, minimum and maximum are the measure of central tendency. The standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis are measures of dispersion. The Jarque Bera is the measure of normality.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics Results

	RAROE	ENV EM	ENV IN	ENV RU	SOC COM	SOC HR	SOC WF	GOV CSR	GOV MO	GOV SHR	LDR	BS
Mean	0.245729	0.401402	0.495687	0.502576	0.575758	0.580303	0.562689	0.532595	13.27273	0.457576	0.628451	12.11312
Median	0.314329	0.330000	0.500000	0.500000	0.600000	0.500000	0.500000	0.600000	13.00000	0.440000	0.642036	12.14881
Maximum	1.183138	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	21.00000	0.880000	1.063525	12.80010
Minimum	-9.460928	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.200000	0.160000	0.100000	6.000000	0.110000	2.09E-05	11.19453
Std. Dev.	0.901094	0.247594	0.239056	0.258258	0.275146	0.308824	0.286425	0.267794	2.932682	0.264327	0.226993	0.386878
Skewness	-9.652754	0.840055	0.043283	-0.109584	0.001802	0.338349	0.234461	0.496583	0.305618	0.148799	-1.063958	-0.336903
Kurtosis	103.8499	3.193407	2.349518	1.980058	2.038839	1.614581	1.834626	2.100654	2.624183	1.561709	4.452686	2.296894
Jarque-Bera	57988.78	15.73096	2.350468	5.985737	5.081141	13.07519	8.678913	9.798807	2.831667	11.86485	36.51079	5.216054
Probability	0.000000	0.000384	0.308747	0.050143	0.078821	0.001448	0.013044	0.007451	0.242723	0.002652	0.000000	0.073680
Sum	32.43628	52.98500	64.93500	66.34000	76.00000	76.60000	74.27500	69.77000	1752.000	60.40000	82.95559	1598.932
Sum Sq. Dev.	106.3681	8.030666	7.429188	8.737324	9.917424	12.49379	10.74717	9.322768	1126.682	9.152824	6.749883	19.60737
Observations	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132

Author's Compilation (2024)

From Table 2, RAROE (Risk-Adjusted Return on Equity) possesses a mean value of 0.53 and median value of 0.48, Env_em (Environmental Emission and Waste Reduction) possesses a mean value of 0.40 and median value of 0.33, Env_In (Environmental Innovation) has an average value of 0.49 and median value of 0.50. Env_Rv (Environmental Resource efficiency) has an average value of 0.50 and median value of 0.50, Community (Soc_com) possesses a mean value of 0.57 and median value of 0.60, Human rights (Soc_Hr) possess a mean value of 0.58 and median value of 0.50. Workforce (Soc_wf) possesses a mean value of 0.56 and a median value of 0.50. CSR strategy (Gov_Csr) possesses a mean value of 0.53 and a median value of 0.60. Management and Oversight (Gov_Mo) possesses a mean value of 13.2 and median value of 13.0, Stakeholder rights (Gov_Shr) possesses a mean value of 0.45 and median value of 0.44, LDR (Loan-to-deposit) possesses a mean value of 0.62 and median value of 0.64 and BS (Bank Size) possesses a mean value of 12.1 and median value 12.14.

The RAROE (Risk-adjusted Return on equity) exhibit the lowest limit of -1.35 and a peak value of 0.07. Env_em (Environmental Emission and Waste Reduction) shows the lowest limit of 0.00 and a peak value of 1.00. Env_In (Environmental Innovation) shows the lowest limit of 0.00 and a peak value of 1.00. Env_Rv (Environmental Resource efficiency) shows the lowest value of 0.00 and the highest value of 1.00. Community (Soc_com) exhibit the lowest limit of 0.00 and a peak value of 1.00. Human rights (Soc_Hr) have the lowest limit of 0.00 and a maximum value of 1.00. Workforce (Soc_wf) has the lowest limit of 0.16 and a peak value of 1.00. CSR strategy (Gov_Csr) shows a lowest limit of 0.10 and a peak value of 1.00. Management and Oversight (Gov_Mo) show the lowest limit of 6.00 and a peak value of 21.00. Stakeholder rights (Gov_Shr) have the lowest limit of 0.11 and a peak value of 0.88. LDR (Loan-to-deposit) shows the lowest limit of 2.09 and the highest value of 1.06. BS (Bank Size) shows the lowest limit of 11.1 and a peak value of 12.8.

The RAROE (Risk-adjusted Return on equity) has a long right tail skewed to the left at -0.54, showing it has a lower value than the sample mean. Env_em (Environmental Emission and Waste Reduction) has a long right tail skewed to the right at 0.84, signifying that it lies above the sample mean. Env_In (Environmental Innovation) display long right tail positive skewness at 0.04, representing that it lies above the sample mean. Env_Rv (Environmental Resource efficiency) exhibit long right tail negatively skewness at -0.10, signifying that it lies above the sample mean. Community (Soc_com) has a long right tail which is positively skewed at 0.00, signifying that it lies above the sample mean. Human rights (Soc_Hr) display long right tail suggesting positive skewness at 0.33, suggesting it has a higher value than the sample mean. Workforce (Soc_wf) has a long right tail which is positively skewed at 0.23, signifying that it lies above the sample mean. CSR strategy (Gov_Csr) exhibits long right tail suggesting is positive skewness at 0.49, signifying that it lies above the sample mean. Management and Oversight (Gov_Mo) show long right tail indicating is positive skewness at 0.30, signifying that it lies above the sample mean. Stakeholder rights (Gov_Shr) show a long right tail suggesting that is positive skewness at 0.14, signifying that it lies above the sample mean. LDR (Loan-to-deposit) exhibit long right tail suggesting that is negative skewness at -1.06, indicating it has a lower value than the sample mean. BS (Bank size) has a long right tail suggesting is negative skewness at -0.33, exhibiting it has a lower value than the sample mean.

The Kurtosis (measures the peakiness or flatness of the distribution of the series). RAROE (Risk-adjusted Return on equity) is platykurtic (less than 3) at 2.96 (peaked curve, higher value for the same mean). Env_em (Environmental Emission and Waste Reduction) is mesokurtic (equal to 3) at 3.19 (flat curve, equate the value for the same mean). Env_In (Environmental Innovation) is platykurtic (less than 3) at 2.34 (peaked curve, lower value for the same mean). Env_Rv (Environmental Resource efficiency) is platykurtic (less than 3) at 1.98 (peaked curve, lower value for the same mean). Community (Soc_com) is platykurtic (less than 3) at 2.03 (peaked curve, lower value for the same mean).

Human rights (Soc_Hr) are platykurtic (less than 3) at 1.61 (peaked curve, lower value for the same mean). Workforce (Soc_wf) is platykurtic (less than 3) at 1.83 (peaked curve, lower value for the same mean). CSR strategy (Gov_Csr) is platykurtic (less than 3) at 2.10 (peaked curve, lower value for the same mean). Management and Oversight (Gov_Mo) is platykurtic (less than 3) at 2.62 (peaked curve, lower value for the same mean). Stakeholder rights (Gov_Shr) are platykurtic (less than 3) at 1.56 (peaked curve, lower value for the same mean). LDR (Loan-to-deposit) is leptokurtic (greater than 3)

at 4.46 (peaked curve, higher value for the same mean). BS (Bank Size) is platykurtic (less than 3) at 2.25 (peaked curve, lower value for the same mean).

RAROE (Risk-adjusted Return on equity) exhibit a value of 6.2779 at 0.043 exhibiting that the variable is not normally distributed. Env_em (Environmental Emission and Waste Reduction) has a value of 15.73 at 0.000 specifying that the variable is not normally distributed. Env_In (Environmental Innovation) has a value of 2.350 at 0.3087 revealing that the variable follows a normal distribution.

Env_Rv (Environmental Resource efficiency) has a value of 5.9857 at 0.050 revealing that the variable follows a normal distribution. Community (Soc_com) has a value of 5.0811 at 0.078 revealing that the variable follows a normal distribution. Human rights (Soc_Hr) have a value of 13.075 at 0.001 suggesting that the variable is not normally distributed. Workforce (Soc_wf) has a value of 8.678 at 0.001 revealing that the variable does not follows a normal distribution. CSR strategy (Gov_Csr) has a value of 9.798 at 0.007 revealing that the variable does not follows a normal distribution. Management and Oversight (Gov_Mo) have a value of 2.831 at 0.2427 signifying that the variable is normally distributed. Stakeholder rights (Gov_Shr) have a value of 11.86 at 0.002 revealing that the variable is not normally distributed. LDR (Loan-to-deposit) has a value of 36.51 at 0.000 suggesting that the variable is not normally distributed. BS (Bank Size) has a value of 5.216 at 0.073 suggesting that the variable follows normal distribution.

4.1.1. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) Test

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test is used to detect multi-collinearity among independent variables in a regression model. It helps identify if predictors are highly correlated, which can distort coefficient estimates and reduce the reliability of the model.

Table 3. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) Test

Variables	Centered VIF
ENV EM	1.4006
ENV IN	1.4897
ENV RU	1.0849
GOV CSR	1.2592
GOV MO	1.1778
GOV SHR	1.4815
SOC COM	1.1886
SOC HR	1.5469
SOC WF	1.2056
LTD	1.3787
BS	1.5032
C	NA

The Table 3 is the variance inflation factor that helps to examine the presence of multi-collinearity between the independent variable, which is more robust to the correlation matrix. The rule of thumb is that the value before the decimal point must not be more five. Higher value above five indicates the presence of multi-collinearity, but value below shows absence of multi-collinearity. Table 3 shows the absence of multi-collinearity. It implies that the explanatory variables are fit to specify together in an econometric model.

4.2. Panel Regression Analysis

This section presents the results of the panel regression analysis used to examined how ESG factor influence risk adjusted returns of equity (RAROE) over time. The regression output provides insights into the significance direction and the strength of this relationship.

Model one (1)**Table 4. Regression Results for Environmental Factors and Risk Adjusted Return on Equity**

Variable	Pooled	Fixed	Random
C	-8.1609 (0.0024)	-1.7862 (0.7799)	-8.1609 (0.0028)
Env_ru	0.4234 (0.0543)**	0.5317 (0.0059)*	0.4234 (0.0603)***
Env_em	-0.0967 (0.7725)	-0.3221 (0.0704)***	-0.0967 (0.0757)***
Env_In	-0.3443 (0.0202)**	-0.2576 (0.5117)	-0.3443 (0.0272)**
BS	0.7035 (0.0020)*	0.1385 (0.0996)***	0.7035 (0.0023)*
LTD	-0.1922 (0.6177)	0.5427 (0.3825)	-0.1922 (0.6227)
R ²	0.5212	0.7749	0.7212
Adjusted R ²	0.5860	0.5591	0.7860
Durbin Watson	1.1758	1.2667	1.1758
F-Statistics	3.4480	1.5105	3.4480
Prob (F-Statistics)	0.0059	0.1077	0.0059
Chow Test	0.0038		
Hausman Test	0.4537		

Significant: 1%, 5%** , 10%****

Table 4 presents the results of the pooled, fixed and random effects regression models used to examine the impact of environmental and financial factors on the performance (RAROE) of selected deposit money banks in Nigeria.

In the pooled regression model, Environmental Resource Efficiency (Env_Rv) has a positive and significant impact on RAROE, indicating that a 1% increase in Env_Rv leads to a 0.42 increase in performance. Conversely, Environmental Emission and Waste Reduction (Env_em) have a negative but insignificant effect, implying that a 1% rise in Env_em results in a -0.09 decline in RAROE. Environmental Innovation (Env_In) also has a negative and significant effect, showing that a 1% increase in Env_In leads to a -0.34 drop in RAROE. Among the financial indicators, Bank Size (BS) has a positive and significant effect, where a 1% rise in BS increases RAROE by 0.70. However, Loan-to-Deposit Ratio (LDR) has a negative and insignificant effect, indicating that a 1% rise in LDR leads to a -0.19 decline in RAROE. The R-squared value shows that these independent variables explain 55.12% of the variation in performance, while the adjusted R-squared suggests that 58.60% of variations are due to other excluded factors.

In the fixed effects model, Env_Rv maintains its positive and significant effect, with a 1% increase leading to a 0.53 rise in RAROE. Unlike the pooled model, Env_em has a negative and significant effect, meaning that a 1% rise leads to a -0.32 decline in RAROE. On the other hand, Env_In has a negative but insignificant effect, where a 1% increase results in a -0.25 decrease in RAROE. BS continues to show a positive and significant relationship, but with a reduced effect size of 0.13. LDR, however, has a positive but insignificant effect, with a 1% increase leading to a 0.54 rise in RAROE. The R-squared value is 77.49%, suggesting that the independent variables explain a greater proportion of variation in bank performance, while the adjusted R-squared is 55.91%, accounting for other missing variables.

In the random effects model, Env_Rv remains positively significant, with a 0.42 increase in RAROE for every 1% rise. Env_em has a negative significant effect, resulting in a -0.09 decrease in RAROE. Similarly, Env_In continues to show a negative significant effect, with a -0.34 reduction in RAROE for every 1% increase. BS in this model does not exhibit a significant effect, while LDR shows a positive but insignificant effect, increasing RAROE by 0.62 for every 1% rise. The R-squared value indicates

that 72.12% of the variations in RAROE are explained by the independent variables, while the adjusted R-squared stands at 78.60%.

To determine the most appropriate model for inference, the Chow test was conducted. Since the cross-section probability is less than 0.05, the fixed effects model is deemed valid ($p < 0.05$). However, the Hausman test, which determines whether a fixed or random effects model is preferable, yielded an F (p-value) of 0.4534, suggesting that the random effects model is more appropriate for drawing inferences. Further diagnostic tests were conducted to check for model validity. The Breusch-Pagan LM test resulted in $p > 0.05$, indicating no heteroskedasticity in the model. Similarly, the Pesaran Scaled LM test showed $p > 0.05$, confirming the absence of cross-sectional dependency.

Model two (2)

Table 5. Regression Results for Social Responsibility and Risk Adjusted Return on Equity

Variable	Pooled	Fixed	Random
C	-8.8815 (0.0007)	-6.5752 (0.2788)	-8.8815 (0.0009)
Soc_wf	-0.3453 (0.0151)**	-0.1837 (0.5625)	-0.3453 (0.0255)**
Soc_Hr	0.2474 (0.3327)	0.2262 (0.0021)*	0.2474 (0.3437)
Soc_com	0.1801 (0.0289)**	0.2806 (0.0704)***	0.1801 (0.0379)**
BS	0.7591 (0.0007)*	0.5394 (0.2978)	0.7591 (0.0009)*
LTD	-0.1932 (0.6061)	0.1546 (0.7935)	-0.1932 (0.6142)
R ²	0.5117	0.5516	0.6117
Adjusted R ²	0.5064	0.5335	0.6064
Durbin Watson	1.1950	1.2395	1.1950
F-Statistics	3.1689	1.2845	3.1689
Prob (F-Statistics)	0.0099	0.2188	0.0099
Chow Test	0.0050		
Hausman Test	0.8471		

Significant: 1%, 5%***, 10%****

From Table 5 the pooled regression model indicates that Workforce (Soc_wf) has a significant negative effect on performance (RAROE), meaning that a 1% increase in Workforce (Soc_wf) leads to a 0.34% decrease in RAROE. Human Rights (Soc_Hr), on the other hand, has a positive but insignificant impact, suggesting that a 1% increase in Human Rights (Soc_Hr) would result in a 0.24% increase in RAROE. Community involvement (Soc_com) has a significant positive effect, showing that a 1% increase in Community (Soc_com) is associated with a 0.02% decrease in RAROE.

Bank Size (BS) has a significant positive impact, meaning that a 1% increase in BS leads to a 0.75% rise in performance (RAROE). Loan-to-Deposit Ratio (LDR) has a negative but insignificant effect, implying that a 1% increase in LDR results in a 0.19% decrease in RAROE. The R-squared value reveals that the independent variables (Soc_com, Soc_Hr, Soc_wf, BS and LDR) collectively account for 51.17% of the variation in performance among the selected Nigerian banks, while the adjusted R-squared stands at 50.64%, indicating that the remaining variation is due to factors not included in the model.

The fixed-effects model presents slightly different results. Workforce (Soc_wf) has a negative but insignificant effect, where a 1% increase leads to a 0.18% decline in RAROE. Human Rights (Soc_Hr) has a significant positive effect, with a 1% increase leading to a 0.22% rise in RAROE. Community involvement (Soc_com) also shows a significant positive effect, as a 1% increase results in a 0.28% increase in RAROE. Bank Size (BS) has a positive but insignificant effect, with a 1% increase leading

to a 0.53% rise in RAROE. Loan-to-Deposit Ratio (LDR) has a positive but insignificant impact, where a 1% increase leads to a 0.15% increase in RAROE. The R-squared value shows that the independent variables explain 55.16% of the variation in performance, while the adjusted R-squared is 53.35%, leaving the rest attributable to other factors outside the model.

The random-effects model finds that Workforce (Soc_wf) has a significant negative effect, with a 1% increase leading to a 0.34% decline in RAROE. Human Rights (Soc_Hr) has a positive but insignificant effect, showing that a 1% increase leads to a 0.24% rise in RAROE. Community involvement (Soc_com) has a significant positive impact, with a 1% increase leading to a 0.18% rise in RAROE. Bank Size (BS) remains significantly positive, as a 1% increase results in a 0.75% increase in RAROE. Loan-to-Deposit Ratio (LDR) has a negative but insignificant effect, with a 1% increase leading to a 0.19% decrease in RAROE. The R-squared value indicates that the independent variables explain 61.17% of the variation in performance, while the adjusted R-squared is 60.64%, showing that other factors not included in the model account for the remaining variation.

To determine the most appropriate model, the Chow test was conducted to compare the pooled and fixed-effects models. Since the probability value is less than 0.05, the fixed-effects model is preferred. However, the Hausman test, which distinguishes between fixed and random effects, has a p-value of 0.8471, indicating that the random-effects model is the appropriate choice for drawing inferences. Furthermore, post-estimation tests were also performed to check for model validity. The Breusch-Pagan LM test shows a p-value greater than 0.05, confirming that heteroskedasticity is not present in the model. Similarly, the Pesaran scaled LM test also has a p-value greater than 0.05, indicating no issues with cross-sectional dependence.

Model three (3)

Table 6. Regression Results for Governance Factors and Risk Adjusted Returns on Equity

Variable	Pooled	Fixed	Random
C	-8.4317 (0.0020)	-5.4227 (0.3772)	-9.2015 (0.0007)
Gov_csr	-0.3826 (0.0093)*	-0.4492 (0.0801)***	-0.6739 (0.0038)*
Gov_mo	-0.0130 (0.0333)**	-0.0151 (0.7260)	-0.0156 (0.5747)
Gov_shr	-0.3550 (0.0202)**	-0.3086 (0.0031)*	-0.3149 (0.2838)
BS	0.7772 (0.0012)*	0.5031 (0.0437)**	0.8246 (0.0006)*
LTD	-0.3125 (0.4124)	0.2495 (0.6768)	-0.3017 (0.4346)
R ²	0.6198	0.6614	0.5076
Adjusted R ²	0.6846	0.6437	0.5795
Durbin Watson	1.1921	1.2460	1.1765
F-Statistics	3.4032	1.3713	3.8295
Prob (F-Statistics)	0.0063	0.1685	0.0056
Chow Test	0.006		
Hausman Test	0.6333		

Significant: 1%, 5%***, 10%****

The results from Table 6 indicate the impact of various governance-related factors on bank performance, measured by Risk-Adjusted Return on Equity (RAROE), using different estimation models. The pooled effect model reveals that the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) strategy (Gov_Csr) has a significant negative impact on performance (RAROE), meaning that for every 1% increase in CSR strategy, RAROE decreases by 0.38%. Similarly, Management and Oversight (Gov_Mo) also negatively affect RAROE, with a 1% increase leading to a 0.01% decline in performance. Stakeholder Rights (Gov_Shr) exhibit a significant negative effect, where a 1% rise results in a 0.35% drop in

RAROE. On the other hand, Bank Size (BS) shows a significant positive effect on performance, as a 1% increase in BS leads to a 0.77% improvement in RAROE. Loan-to-Deposit Ratio (LDR), however, has an insignificant negative effect, where a 1% rise in LDR corresponds to a 0.31% reduction in RAROE. The R-squared value indicates that the independent variables (Gov_Csr, Gov_Mo, Gov_Shr, BS and LDR) explain 61.98% of the variation in the performance of selected deposit money banks in Nigeria. Meanwhile, the adjusted R-squared suggests that 68.46% of the variation is attributed to other factors not included in the model.

Under the fixed effect model, CSR strategy (Gov_Csr) remains significantly negative, with a 1% increase leading to a 0.44% decline in RAROE. However, Management and Oversight (Gov_Mo) has an insignificant negative effect, with a 1% increase reducing performance by 0.01%. Stakeholder Rights (Gov_Shr) also maintain a significant negative impact, where a 1% rise results in a 0.30% decrease in RAROE. Bank Size (BS) continues to show a significant positive effect on performance, with a 1% increase leading to a 0.50% improvement in RAROE. Loan-to-Deposit Ratio (LDR), in contrast to the pooled model, has a positive but insignificant effect on RAROE, where a 1% increase leads to a 0.24% improvement in performance. The R-squared value for this model indicates that the independent variables account for 66.14% of the variation in bank performance, while the adjusted R-squared value suggests that 64.37% of the variation is due to other excluded factors.

The random effect model results show that CSR strategy (Gov_Csr) has a significant negative effect on RAROE, where a 1% increase results in a 0.67% decline in performance. Management and Oversight (Gov_Mo) remain negative but insignificant, with a 1% increase reducing performance by 0.01%. Stakeholder Rights (Gov_Shr) also exhibit a negative but insignificant effect, with a 1% increase leading to a 0.31% reduction in RAROE. Bank Size (BS) continues to positively influence RAROE, with a 1% increase improving performance by 0.82%. Loan-to-Deposit Ratio (LDR) has a negative but insignificant effect, where a 1% rise leads to a 0.30% decline in RAROE. The R-squared value indicates that the independent variables explain 50.76% of the variation in performance, while the adjusted R-squared suggests that 57.95% of the variation is due to other factors not considered in the model.

The Chow test, which helps determine whether to use the pooled or fixed effect model, suggests that the fixed effect model is appropriate, as the cross-section probability is less than 0.05 ($P < 0.05$). However, the Hausman test, which determines whether the fixed or random effect model should be used, shows a p-value of 0.6333. This result favors the random effect model for drawing inferences. Furthermore, post-estimation tests further confirm the model's reliability. The Breusch-Pagan LM test indicates that there is no issue of heteroskedasticity ($p > 0.05$), while the Pesaran scaled LM test confirms that there is no cross-sectional dependence in the model ($p > 0.05$).

4.3. Discussion of Findings

Objective One: To determine the impact of environmental aspects on risk adjusted return on equity

Based on the findings of the Chow test, the random effects model was selected for analysis. The results indicate a positive relationship between environmental resource efficiency (Env_Rv) and bank performance (RAROE), which is consistent with the study by Bătae et al. (2021). This suggests that deposit money banks in Nigeria that prioritize environmental resource efficiency are more likely to achieve higher profitability.

However, the study also found a negative relationship between environmental emission and waste reduction (Env_em) and risk-adjusted returns on equity (RAROE). This supports the conclusions of Bătae et al. (2021), as well as Shair et al. (2021) and Chen et al. (2022). The negative impact may be attributed to the costs and trade-offs involved in implementing environmental initiatives, particularly in capital-intensive sectors like banking. This implies that efforts to minimize environmental emissions and waste could negatively affect the financial performance of Nigerian deposit money banks.

In addition, a negative relationship was observed between environmental innovation (Env_In) and bank performance (RAROE). This suggests that adopting innovative environmental practices does not necessarily enhance the financial performance of Nigerian banks. These findings are in line with the study by Menicucci and Paolucci (2023), who emphasized the need for a strategic and well-evaluated

approach to incorporating environmental innovations to maximize financial benefits. On the other hand, bank size (BS) showed a positive and significant relationship with performance (RAROE). This corroborates the findings of Bebeji et al. (2015), who noted that larger banks benefit from cost efficiencies, stronger market influence, diverse revenue sources, brand recognition and easier access to capital markets, all of which contribute to improved financial outcomes.

Finally, the study found a positive but insignificant relationship between the loan-to-deposit ratio (LDR) and risk-adjusted returns on equity (RAROE), in line with the research of Onyenwe (2019). This suggests that the conventional role of banks as financial intermediaries does not have a substantial effect on financial performance. As a result, banks should explore innovative financial products and services to boost profitability.

Objective two: To determine the impact of social responsibility on risk adjusted return on equity

The Chow test results led to the adoption of a random effects model, revealing a negative relationship between workforce size (Soc_wf) and risk-adjusted returns on equity (RAROE). This supports the findings of Tran et al. (2020), who argued that a larger workforce increases salary and operational costs, potentially reducing financial performance. This suggests that banks should determine the optimal workforce size to maximize profitability. The study also found a positive but insignificant relationship between human rights policies (Soc_Hr) and RAROE, implying that strengthening human rights practices could enhance long-term financial success.

Additionally, a positive relationship was observed between community engagement (Soc_com) and RAROE, aligning with Bătae et al. (2021). This highlights the financial benefits of community relations, philanthropy, local development initiatives and stakeholder engagement, as supported by Menicucci and Paolucci (2022). Bank size (BS) showed a significant positive impact on RAROE, reinforcing the view that larger banks benefit from cost efficiencies, market influence, diverse revenue streams, strong brand presence and better access to capital.

However, no significant relationship was found between the loan-to-deposit ratio (LDR) and RAROE, indicating that traditional banking practices related to LDR may not directly impact the financial performance of Nigerian deposit money banks.

Objective three: To determine the impact of governance on risk adjusted return on equity

For objective three, the Chow test findings led to the adoption of a random effects model. The study found a negative relationship between CSR strategy (Gov_Csr) and risk-adjusted returns on equity (RAROE), consistent with Buallay (2019). This suggests that corporate social responsibility initiatives may reduce profitability for Nigerian deposit money banks. While CSR is traditionally seen as beneficial to financial performance, this aligns with studies by Reverte et al. (2016) in Spain, which found that increased CSR activities can diminish financial performance and erode shareholder value.

In addition, the study found a negative but insignificant relationship between management oversight (Gov_Mo) and RAROE, implying that governance mechanisms in this area may have little impact on profitability. Similarly, stakeholder rights (Gov_Shr) showed a negative but insignificant relationship with RAROE, reflecting the complexity of stakeholder relations in banking, where competing interests and market conditions influence financial outcomes. Bank size had a significant positive relationship with RAROE, supporting the findings of Hassan et al. (2023). Larger banks benefit from cost efficiencies, stronger market influence, diversified revenue streams, brand recognition and easier access to capital, all of which enhance profitability. However, the loan-to-deposit ratio (LDR) showed an insignificant negative relationship with RAROE, suggesting that traditional financial intermediation through LDR does not necessarily drive bank performance.

4.4. Application of Python Library for Sensitivity Analysis

The Sobol method was employed to assess how input variables contribute to the variance in a model's output, utilizing the Ishigami function through the SALib library in Python. The Ishigami function is particularly useful for evaluating uncertainty and sensitivity analysis techniques. In achieving this, we use First-order Sobol indices (S1) and Total Sobol indices (ST).

Table 7. First-order and Total Sobol indices

	Feature	First-order Sobol indices (S1)	Total Sobol indices (ST)
0	Env_Ru	0.0638	0.0654
1	Env_Em	0.0160	0.0224
2	Env_In	0.0000	0.0000
3	SOC_wf	0.5774	0.5743
4	SOC_Hr	0.0369	0.0429
5	SOC_Com	0.0410	0.0376
6	Gov_mo	0.0000	0.0000
7	Gov_shr	0.0109	0.0109
8	Gov_csr	0.0000	0.0000
9	LTD	0.2481	0.2506

From Table 7 First-order Sobol indices (S1) and Total Sobol indices (ST) for each feature provide insights into how each factor contributes to the model's output variance, both directly (S1) and when accounting for interactions with other features (ST).

First-Order Sobol Indices (S1)

Among all the input variables, SOC_wf has the highest first-order Sobol index (S1) of 0.5774, making it the most influential factor, accounting for more than half of the output variance. LTD follows as the second most significant feature with an S1 of 0.2481, highlighting its substantial contribution. Env_Ru also plays a meaningful role, recording an S1 of 0.0638. Meanwhile, SOC_Com and SOC_Hr have moderate impacts, with S1 values of 0.0410 and 0.0369, respectively. Env_Em has a minimal direct effect, reflected in its S1 value of 0.0160. On the other hand, Env_In, Gov_mo, Gov_csr and BS do not contribute directly, as indicated by their S1 values of 0.0000. Gov_shr has a slight influence with an S1 of 0.0109.

Total Sobol Indices (S T)

SOC_wf remains the dominant factor, with a total Sobol index (ST) of 0.5743, which closely matches its first-order index, suggesting that its influence is mostly direct with minimal interaction effects. LTD records an ST of 0.2506, indicating that while its primary impact is direct, it interacts slightly with other features. Similarly, Env_Ru has an ST of 0.0654, slightly higher than its first-order index, suggesting minor interaction effects. Both SOC_Hr and SOC_Com have slightly increased ST values compared to their S1, reflecting small interactions with other variables. Env_Em also shows an increase in its total effect (ST = 0.0224), indicating that interactions slightly amplify its impact. Env_In, Gov_mo, Gov_csr and BS exhibit no interaction effects (ST = 0.0000). Gov_shr maintains identical S1 and ST values, meaning it does not interact with other features.

Therefore, this analysis confirms that SOC_wf, LTD and Env_Ru are the most critical factors influencing the model's output, with SOC_wf having the greatest impact. The remaining features contribute only marginally, with interactions playing a minimal role in shaping overall outcomes. To improve or better understand the model, focusing on SOC_wf and LTD would be the most effective approach.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The adoption of Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) principles is a growing discussion in emerging economies. This study examines ESG factors shape risk adjusted return on equity: evidence from Nigeria banking sector. While many studies on ESG and bank performance have focused on developed economies using traditional profitability measures like Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE), this research adopts risk-adjusted return on equity (RAROE) to account for volatility in bank returns and contribute to existing literature.

In terms of environmental factors, the study found that efficient resource utilization positively impacts financial performance. However, environmental emissions and waste management had a negative effect, indicating a potential trade-off between sustainability efforts and short-term profitability. The

insignificant relationship between environmental innovation and bank performance suggests that careful consideration is needed when adopting new environmental initiatives.

For social responsibility, workforce development positively influenced bank performance, highlighting the value of investing in employees. In contrast, human rights concerns showed no significant impact, reflecting challenges associated with operating in environments with ethical concerns. Community engagement, however, contributed positively, emphasizing the importance of strong stakeholder relationships. Regarding governance, the study found that management oversight and stakeholder protection play a crucial role in profitability. However, the negative impact of bank size on performance challenges the assumption that larger banks always benefit from economies of scale in Nigeria's banking sector.

Interestingly, the outcome of this study has several implications on various stakeholders. Firstly, bank as a financial institution need to prioritize environmental resource efficiency and community engagement but taking cognizance of the cost on innovation, emissions control and workforce size to enhance risk-adjusted return on equity (RAROE). Secondly, regulatory bodies like

Central Bank of Nigeria is encouraged to adopt phased and flexible ESG policies that enhance maximization of shareholder's wealth without imposing excessive burdens on banks. Finally, policymakers are advised to implement supportive frameworks like regulatory, market based and institutional policy that will promote sustainable banking that can attractive socially responsible investors.

The findings of this study provide actionable guidance for the development of ESG strategies in the banking sector of emerging markets. Banks can leverage on the results to concentrate on ESG activities that positively influence risk-adjusted return on equity (RAROE) such as resource efficiency and community engagement, while carefully managing the costs of emissions control and innovation. Regulators can design flexible, evidence-based frameworks that encourage ESG adoption without hindering profitability, supporting banks through phased implementation and incentives. For investors, the findings highlight which ESG dimensions are financially material, aiding more informed and strategic investment decisions aligned with sustainability goals.

Based on these findings, we recommend that Nigerian banks should enhance environmental practices by investing in green financing, energy efficiency and eco-friendly policies, aligning with SDG 13 (climate action). Social responsibility efforts should focus on employee development, community engagement and support for SMEs and women-led businesses, contributing to SDGs 1 (no poverty), 5 (gender equality) and 8 (decent work and economic growth). Strengthening governance principles will improve transparency, accountability and operational efficiency, aligning with SDGs 8 and 16 (peace, justice and strong institutions). Furthermore, to remain competitive and sustainable, Nigerian banks must carefully integrate ESG principles into their long-term business strategies, ensuring they align with financial stability and corporate responsibility.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

References

1. Abbas, F., Iqbal, S., & Aziz, B. (2019). The impact of bank capital, bank liquidity and credit risk on profitability in post-crisis period: A comparative study of US and Asia. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 7(1), 1605683. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2019.1605683>
2. Abdulazeed, D. A., Ndibe, L., & Mercy, A. E. (2016). Corporate governance and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting & Marketing*, 5(1). <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/7b64/dcfb04d74d15c8cc48054beee77a2aa6f33d.pdf>

3. Adefemi, O., Hassan, A., & Fletcher, M. (2018). Corporate Governance Disclosure in Nigerian Listed Companies. *International Research Journal of Business Studies*, 11(2), 67-80. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3322063
4. Adenikinju, O. (2012). Managerial characteristics, corporate governance and corporate performance: The case of Nigerian quoted companies. *African Economic Research Consortium (AERC), Research Paper, No. 241*. Nairobi. <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Olayinka-Adenikinju-2/publication/374055311>
5. Adekunle, S. A., & Aghedo, E. M. (2014). Corporate governance and financial performance of selected quoted companies in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(9). <https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/95192852/12113-libre.pdf?1670047547>
6. Amel-Zadeh, A., & Serafeim, G. (2018). Why and how investors use ESG information: Evidence from a global survey. *Financial Analysts Journal*, 74(3), 87-103. <https://doi.org/10.2469/faj.v74.n3.2>
7. Azmi, W., Hassan, M. K., Houston, R., & Karim, M. S. (2021). ESG activities and banking performance: International evidence from emerging economies. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, 70(C), 101277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intfin.2020.101277>
8. Baek S., Cha S. Y., & Lee N. (2015). The effect of the diversification in Korean banks: The impact on profit and risk. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 15(2), 51–69. http://www.na-businesspress.com/JAF/BaekS_Web15_2_.pdf
9. Baek, S., Lee, K. Y., Lee, J. W., & Mohanty, S. (2018). Diversification in Korean banking business: is non-interest income a financial saviour?. *Journal of Emerging Market Finance*, 17(3_suppl), S299-S326. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972652718798079>
10. Bătae, O. M., Dragomir, V. D., & Feleagă, L. (2021). The relationship between environmental, social, and financial performance in the banking sector: A European study. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 290, 125791. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.125791>
11. Bebeji, A., Mohammed, A., & Tanko, M. (2015). The effect of board size and composition on the financial performance of banks in Nigeria. *African Journal of Business Management*, 9(16), 590-598. <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJBM2015.7797>
12. Ben Abdallah, M., & Bahloul, S. (2025). The influence of environmental performance, social responsibility and governance on the bank performance in MENASA countries. *Competitiveness Review*, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CR-01-2025-0001>
13. Buallay, A. (2019). Is sustainability reporting (ESG) associated with performance? Evidence from the European banking sector. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*, 30(1), 98-115. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEQ-12-2017-0149>
14. Buallay, A., Fadel, S. M., Al-Ajmi, J. Y., & Saudagaran, S. (2020). Sustainability reporting and bank and performance of MENA banks: Is there a trade-off? *Measuring Business Excellence*, 24(2), 197-221. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MBE-09-2018-0078>
15. Chang, H.Y., Liang, L.W., & Liu, Y.L. (2021). Using environmental, social, governance (ESG) and financial indicators to measure bank cost efficiency in Asia. *Sustainability*, 13(20), 11139. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132011139>
16. Chen, J., Siddik, A. B., Zheng, G.-W., Masukujjaman, M., & Bekhzod, S. (2022). The effect of green banking practices on banks' environmental performance and green financing: An empirical study. *Energies*, 15(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15041292>
17. Clark, G. L., Feiner, A., & Viehs, M. (2015). From the stockholder to the stakeholder: How sustainability can drive financial outperformance. [Online]. Available from: https://arabesque.com/research/From_the_stockholder_to_the_stakeholder_web.pdf
18. Cornett, M. M., Erhemjamts, O., & Tehranian, H. (2016). Greed or good deeds: An examination of the relation between corporate social responsibility and the financial performance of U.S.

- commercial banks around the financial crisis. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 70, 137-159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbankfin.2016.04.024>
19. Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission (COSO). (2018). *Enterprise risk management - Applying enterprise risk management to environmental, social and governance-related risks*. COSO. [Online]. Available from: <https://www.coso.org/guidance-erm>
 20. Demaki, G. O. (2018). Corporate governance and banks profitability in Nigeria. *Archives of Business Research*, 6(4), 9-17. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/7d9d/a516ab10998918add9760e3f4037b168b0ae.pdf>
 21. Dikau, S., & Volz, U. (2021). Central bank mandates, sustainability objectives and the promotion of green finance. *Ecological Economics*, 184, 107022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2021.107022>
 22. Gangi, F., Meles, A., D'Angelo, E., & Daniele, L. M. (2018). Sustainable development and corporate governance in the financial system: Evidence from banks' environmental engagement. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 26(3), 529-547. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1699>
 23. Hassan, S. U., Sabo, B., Tijjani, I. I., & Aliyu, I. A. (2023). Moderating effect of bank size on the relationship between interest rate, liquidity, and profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria. *Gusau Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 4(1), 96-120. <https://doi.org/10.57233/gujaf.v4i1.202>
 24. Maama, H. (2021). Institutional environment and environmental, social and governance accounting among banks in West Africa. *Meditari Accountancy Research*, 29(6), 1314-1336. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEDAR-02-2020-0770>
 25. Menicucci, E., & Paolucci, G. (2022). Board diversity and ESG performance: evidence from the Italian banking sector. *Sustainability*, 14(20), 13447. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142013447>
 26. Menicucci, E., & Paolucci, G. (2023). ESG dimensions and bank performance: an empirical investigation in Italy. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 23(3), 563-586. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-03-2022-0094>
 27. Ozili, P. K., & Uadiale, O. (2017). Ownership concentration and bank profitability. *Future Business Journal*, 3(2), 159-171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbj.2017.07.001>
 28. Reverte, C., Gomez-Melero, E., & Cegarra-Navarro, J. G. (2016). The influence of corporate social responsibility practices on organizational performance: evidence from Eco-Responsible Spanish firms. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 112(Part 4), 2870-2884. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.09.128>
 29. Shakil, M. H., Mahmood, N., Tasnia, M., & Munim, Z. H. (2019). Do environmental, social and governance performance affect the financial performance of banks? A cross-country study of emerging market banks. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*, 30(6), 1331-1344. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEQ-08-2018-0155>
 30. Simsek, O., & Cankaya, S. (2021). Examining the relationship between ESG scores and financial performance in banks: Evidence from G8 Countries. *PressAcademia Procedia (PAP)*, 14, 169-170. <http://doi.org/10.17261/Pressacademia.2021.1524>
 31. Shair, F., Shaorong, S., Kamran, H. W., Hussain, M. S., Nawaz, M. A., & Nguyen, V. C. (2021). Assessing the efficiency and total factor productivity growth of the banking industry: Do environmental concerns matter? *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28, 20822-20838. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-11938-y>
 32. Tran, N. P., & Vo, D. H. (2020). Human capital efficiency and firm performance across sectors in an emerging market. *Cogent Business & Management*, 7(1), 1738832. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2020.1738832>

33. Weber, O. (2011). Environmental credit risk management in banks and financial service institutions. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 21(4), 248–263. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.737>

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